

Design Optimization of a Hybrid Gravity Field Model Based on Vertical Deflections and Gravimetry: Evaluating Machine Learning as an Alternative Approach (Nr. 1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/262)

Version 1

Description

This data management plan describes the handling of research data generated and used within a postdoctoral project focused on gravity field and quasi-geoid modelling in Latvia. The project involves the generation of derived and processed datasets, including model outputs, numerical results, and computational scripts related to gravimetric and vertical deflection analysis. The plan outlines procedures for data collection, processing, storage, documentation, and long-term preservation in accordance with FAIR principles. Research data and associated metadata will be made available through trusted repositories to support transparency, reproducibility, and potential re-use by the geodetic and geoscientific research community.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/262

Researchers

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Organizations
Riga Technical University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Design Optimization of a Hybrid Gravity Field Model Based on Vertical Deflections and Gravimetry: Evaluating Machine Learning as an Alternative Approach (Nr. 1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/262)

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Researchers:

[Katerina Runde \(0000-0003-2303-6818\)](#)

Organizations:

[Riga Technical University](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#) | [LCS](#)

Grants: [1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/262](#)

Project:

3. License

License:

Access Rights: [Restricted](#)

Publication Date:

4. Templates

Descriptions

Design Optimization of a Hybrid Gravity Field Model Based on Vertical Deflections and Gravimetry: Evaluating Machine Learning as an Alternative Approach (Nr. 1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/262)

This description covers research datasets generated and used within a postdoctoral project focused on gravity field and quasi-geoid modelling in Latvia. The datasets include processed and derived numerical data, model results, and computational outputs related to gravimetric observations and vertical deflection analysis. The data are intended to support geodetic research, model validation, and methodological development, and are documented in accordance with FAIR data management principles.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of the data collection and generation is to support gravity field and quasi-geoid modelling in Latvia within a postdoctoral research project. The data are generated through the processing and analysis of gravimetric observations, vertical deflection information, and numerical modelling results. These datasets are used to develop, validate, and assess geodetic models and methodologies.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Survey data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

TXT

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

30

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

Yes

1.1.7 If Yes, please indicate what data set are you re-using?

id: null, Type: other

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data may be useful for researchers in the field of geodesy, geophysics, and Earth sciences, particularly those working on gravity field modelling, quasi-geoid determination, and related geodetic applications.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

Yes

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

3 Resources and Security

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